

THE USE OF UNUSUAL TECHNOLOGIES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE PERSIAN PROCESSES

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Annotation: In this article describes the use of innovative techniques in teaching foreign languages. Information has been provided on the importance of conducting innovative activities in education.

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Nowadays, in the educational process, interest in the application of innovative methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, attention is gaining strength day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until then, in traditional education, a student is taught to master only his finished knowledge, while modern technologies teach students to look for the knowledge they are

Innovation - is innovation, innovation. Innovative technologies are the pedagogical process and the introduction of innovations and changes in the activities of the teacher and student, and in its implementation, mainly interactive methods are fully used.

Interactive methods it is referred to as collective thinking, that is, pedagogical methods of influence are a component of the content of Education. The peculiarity of these methods is that they are carried out only through the joint activities of educators and student-students.

The process of such pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include:

- *The fact that the student-student is able to not be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, create and seek;*
- *Ensure that the student-student constantly has knowledge interests in the learning process;*
- *Organization of the activities of the educator and student-student always in cooperation.*

Innovation develops through the use of research activities aimed at obtaining new scientific knowledge, some kind of discoveries, inventions. In addition, the emergence of innovations can be the result of design work, in which instrumental and technological knowledge develops, reflecting the possibility of carrying out practical actions on the basis of existing scientific theories and concepts. Thus, innovative projects are created, which subsequently lead to the emergence of new technologies.

Innovations also develop in the process of educational activities. In the educational process, theoretical and practical knowledge of students develops, which can then be applied in various areas of practical life related to the creation of innovations.

Innovative educational technologies are based on three main components:

1. Modern, well-structured content, the basis of which is competence in professional activities that meets the current realities of entrepreneurial activity. the content includes various multimedia materials that are transmitted through modern means of communication.

2. Application of modern, innovative teaching methods. Such methods should be aimed at the development of competencies of the future specialist, the involvement of students in active cognitive and practical activities, the manifestation of initiative in the process of cognition. Passive assimilation of educational programs is excluded.

3. The presence of modern infrastructure in the educational process. It should be based on information, technological, organizational and communication components that help to apply new forms and methods of teaching, in particular distance education.

Innovative technologies in education are used on the basis of the application of certain approaches to teaching, i.e. principles that include requirements and goals that are the basis for the development of new technologies.

All innovations in the pedagogical sphere are based on the fact that society strictly corresponds to the current stage of socio-economic development. Currently, they should focus on the development of Students ' Independence, the formation of self-learning and self-development skills, the conscious assimilation of educational programs, and not mechanically. Innovative technologies in the field of education are constantly developing, their types are expanding. The following main groups of technologies can be distinguished:

1. Information and communication technologies or ICT in the field of subject research. The use of these technologies is associated with the development of the information society and the active introduction of Information Media in all spheres of life. Such technologies are aimed at informatizing the minds of students. Educational programs include new disciplines focused on the study of informatics, information processes and ICT. The educational process is also actively informed to help increase the information culture of professors and students;

2. Personality-oriented technologies. These technologies are aimed at prioritizing the individual in training and education. The entire educational process is aimed at the development of personality, taking into account the individuality and development characteristics of the individual.

3. Information and analytical provision of the educational process. The use of this group of technologies is aimed at researching the development of each student, class, parallel, educational institution and adequately assessing them;

4. Intellectual development monitoring. Technologies are based on the use of graphs, a test system, new assessment methods, which allow you to monitor the dynamics of the development of individual students and the quality of education in general;

5. Educational technologies. The educational process cannot be distinguished from upbringing. Therefore, new methods of developing a person, his main qualities are being introduced;

6. Didactic technologies. They are the main factor in the development of an educational institution. Such technologies are based on a complex of techniques and tools that involve the use of traditional and innovative technologies: independent work with educational literature, the use of audiovisual, multimedia, differentiated teaching methods.

Innovative technologies in education make it possible to regulate education and direct it in the right direction. People were always afraid of something unknown and new, they reacted negatively to any changes. Stereotypes that exist in the public consciousness, affecting the usual way of life, lead to painful phenomena, prevent the renewal of all types of Education. The reason why people do not want to accept innovations in modern education lies in blocking vital needs for comfort, security and self-affirmation. Not everyone is ready to re-

learn the theory, take exams, change their mind, spend personal time and money. Once the update process has started, you can stop it using only special methods.

The most common ways to verify the effectiveness of changes initiated in education are:

1. Method of marking documents. To evaluate innovations in the educational system, the possibility of volumetric inclusion of innovations in the educational process is limited. A separate school, university, educational institution are selected and experience is carried out on their basis.
2. Piece-by-piece placement method. This implies the introduction of a separate new innovation element.
3. "Eternal experience" means assessing the results obtained over a long period of time. Innovative technologies in education "slow down" for various reasons.

1. The barrier of creativity. Teachers who are used to working on old programs do not want to change anything, learn and develop. They are hostile to all innovations in the educational system.

2. Compliance. Due to flexibility, unwillingness to develop, fear of looking like a black sheep in the eyes of others, funny appearance, teachers refuse to make unusual pedagogical decisions.

3. Personal concern. Due to self-confidence, ability, strength, low self-esteem, fear of making their own comments open, many teachers resist any changes in the educational institution to the last chance.

4. The rigidity of thinking. Old school teachers see their opinions as single, final, non-revisionable. They do not strive to acquire new knowledge and skills, react negatively to new trends in modern educational institutions.

Innovative behavior does not mean adaptation, it implies the formation of one's own personality, self-development. The teacher should understand that innovative education is a way to educate a harmonious personality. "Ready-made templates" do not suit him, it is important to constantly increase his intellectual level. Getting rid of "complexes" and psychological barriers, the teacher is ready to become a full-fledged participant in innovative changes.

Innovation in education implies a system consisting of several components:

- ❖ *training objectives;*
- ❖ *educational content;*
- ❖ *motivation and training tools;*
- ❖ *process participants (students, teachers);*
- ❖ *performance results.*

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that ICT has become commonplace in kindergartens, schools, academies, universities.

The rapid development of society necessitates the need to change the technologies and methods of the educational process. Graduates of educational institutions should be prepared for changing modern trends. Therefore, the introduction of technologies aimed at an individual approach, mobility and distance in education seems necessary and inevitable.

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